

ORIDONIN EFFECT ON AUTO IMMUNE HEPATITIS INDUCED IN MICE

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ABSTRACT

Background: Oridonin (ORI), a bioactive diterpenoid, exhibits potent anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immunoregulatory activities. Autoimmune hepatitis (AIH) is a chronic immune-mediated liver disease characterized by lymphocyte-driven hepatic inflammation, excessive cytokine production, and progressive liver injury. Given the pharmacological properties of ORI and the need for safe hepatoprotective agents; ORI was anticipated as a potential hepatoprotective agent against AIH. **Objective:** This study was designed to evaluate the protective effects of ORI in a concanavalin A (Con-A)-induced mouse model of AIH, targeting AKT/PI3K/mTOR–NLRP3 inflammatory signaling, oxidative stress, and M1/M2 polarization. **Methods:** Thirty male BALB/c mice were divided into three groups, CTR group, Con-A group, ORI (5 mg/kg) + Con-A group. ORI was administered i.p for 4 days before a single Con-A injection (15 mg/kg i.v.). Liver injury was

examined on the basis of serum liver enzymes, examination of oxidative stress and pro-inflammatory markers. **Results:** ORI pretreatment mitigated Con-A-induced hepatocellular injury, oxidative stress, and. It significantly reduced liver enzyme elevation, suppressed oxidative stress. Furthermore, ORI downregulated IL-6 as pro-inflammatory markers. **Conclusion:** ORI exhibits hepatoprotective potential against Con-A-induced AIH by reducing oxidative stress and inflammation.

KEYWORDS: ORI, AIH, Con-A model, SOD, IL-6.

1. INTRODUCTION

Autoimmune hepatitis (AIH) is chronic inflammation of the liver due to a loss of immune tolerance for hepatic antigen. Lymphocyte infiltration, massive cytokine production, oxidative stress together with progressive hepatocellular injury are the hallmarks of the disease and might eventually lead to fibrosis or cirrhosis and liver failure if not treated.^[1] The con A-induced hepatitis model is widely used as a model for experimental AIH because it closely reflects T-cell-mediated immune response and cytokine-mediated liver injury.^[2]

In immune-mediated Serum alanine aminotransferase (ALT) is a popular and sensitive marker of damage to hepatocytes.^[3] ALT activity elevation is indicative of membrane breakdown as well as cytoplasmic spillover from injured hepatocytes.^[4] Oxidative stress can injure cellular membranes, interfere with mitochondrial function, modify gene expression, induce apoptosis and necrosis of hepatic cells, and contribute to fibrogenesis in a variety of acute and chronic liver diseases, including AIH.^[5] Several mechanisms that relate reactive oxygen (ROS) and in inflammatory liver injury have been implicated to operate pathogenetically in AIH. Meanwhile, oxidative stress is a major pathogenic factor for AIH associated with the production of excessive ROS in the presence of insufficient antioxidant defenses. As one of antioxidant enzyme, superoxide dismutase (SOD) plays an important role in dismutation of the superoxide radical to maintain intracellular redox homeostasis.^[6] A reduction in SOD activity is a characteristic of oxidative stress-induced liver damage.^[7]

Inflammatory cytokines magnify the progression of AIH and interleukin-6 (IL-6) is at core of immune augmentation.^[8] In addition, Sun and colleagues mentioned that IL-6 enhances T-cell activation, shifts the balance of macrophages toward a pro-inflammatory phenotype and it propagates cytokine cascades responsible for exacerbating both hepatocyte apoptosis and necrosis. High IL-6 is significantly correlated to AIH severity. It has been well-described in that Th-17 cells produce proinflammatory reactions.^[9] Th-17 cell subtypes are derived from naive CD4(+) T cells and predominantly produce IL-17A, IL-17F, and GM-CSF. IL-17-producing T cells (Th-17) is induced by IL-6.^[10]

Oridonin (ORI) is a natural tetracyclic diterpenoid which has been widely studied for its anti-inflammatory and antioxidation effects.^[11] It was previously shown to inhibit cytokine release, immune cell activation and redox derangement in inflammatory states.^[11] Research has shown that oridonin can induce the differentiation of T cells to CD4+/CD5+ Tregs, and produce IL-10, regulate Th1/Th2 balance.^[12] Nevertheless, the integrated influence of ORI on

ALT, SOD and IL-6 in autoimmune hepatitis is not well-presented. As such, the goal of this study was to investigate the protective effect of ORI on Con-A–induced liver injury by targeting these three critical biomarkers.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. *Drugs and chemicals*

ORI and Con-A were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, USA. Both of Con-A and ORI were prepared in normal saline (0.9% w/v) immediately prior to administration to the mice. All other chemicals were of analytical purity.

2.2. *Animals and ethical approval*

The experiment involved thirty BALB-C male mice, weighing approximately 30 ± 5 g, 5–7 weeks old. The animals were housed in a specific-pathogen free facility at 24 ± 2 °C, humidity of $55 \pm 8\%$ and on a cycle of 12-h light/dark. The animals had free access to food and water. The animal protocol was approved by the Animal Care and Use Committee (MU-ACUC) (Protocol No.: PHARM. MS.24. 10. 120).

2.3. *Experimental protocol*

Following a 2-week acclimatization period, the mice were randomly assigned to three groups ($n = 6$ /each) as follows.

Control group; normal mice received normal saline (i.p) for four consecutive days and i.v in the fourth day.

Con-A group; Con-A group; mice challenged with Con-A (15 mg/kg; i.v in the tail vein) on the fourth day of the experiment.^[13]

ORI 5 + Con-A group; mice treated with ORI (5 mg/kg, i.p)^[14] for 4 consecutive days then on the fourth day of the experiment, Con-A was injected 2 hrs after administration of ORI.

2.4. *Specimen collection*

Three hours following Con-A injection, the animals were anesthetized using secobarbital (50 mg/kg, i.p.). The blood was drawn from the retro-orbital plexus, and centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 15 min. The serum obtained after centrifugation was immediately employed for hepatic function markers. Liver was dissected and washed with cold 0.9% normal saline after being brought out of deep anesthesia, and liver were employed to prepare 10% w/v liver homogenate in cold phosphate buffered saline (PBS; 0.01 M, pH 7.4). The homogenate was

next subjected to centrifugation (4000 rpm, 15 min., 4°C) using Sigma3K30 HS and the supernatants were used for determination of GSH and IL-6.

2.5. Determination of liver enzymes

Serum levels of ALT were measured in the sera samples using the diagnostic kits (Agappe Diagnostics LTD., Kerela, India).

2.8. Determination of SOD and IL-6

Hepatic SOD activity was measured using commercially available kits (Biodiagnostic; Giza, Egypt). IL-6 was measured using MyBiosource, USA, Cat# MBS824703.

2.11. Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS version 25.0; IBM/SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL). Results were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Normality and homogeneity of variances were assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk and Levene’s tests, respectively. For comparisons among groups, one-way ANOVA was performed, followed by Tukey’s honestly significant difference (Tukey-HSD) *post hoc* test to identify pairwise group differences. A *P*-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Impact of ORI (5 mg/kg) on liver enzymes activity

Table 1 showed the activity of serum ALT enzyme in the tested groups. Con-A treatment resulted in a marked hepatocellular damage as indicated by the significantly raised ALT activity when compared to CTR. Pre-treatment with ORI (5 mg/kg) significantly abrogated serum ALT activity induced by Con-A that observed in the Con-A group.

3.2. Effect of ORI (5 mg/kg) on Hepatic SOD Activity

Hepatic SOD activity was markedly reduced in Con-A–treated mice, reflecting excessive oxidative stress and impaired antioxidant defense. ORI pretreatment significantly restored SOD activity at (table 1).

3.6. Impact of ORI (5 mg/kg) on hepatic expression of IL-6

Con-A induced liver inflammation revealed by significant elevation in IL-6. ORI pretreatment (5 mg/kg) markedly suppressed IL-6 (table 1).

4. DISCUSSION

Autoimmune hepatitis (AIH) is an aggressive immune-mediated liver disorder that involves hyperactivity of T cells, overexpression of cytokines, oxidative stress and chronic damage to hepatocytes. Concanavalin A (Con-A)-induced hepatitis is a widely accepted experimental model that recapitulates the immunopathological aspects of human AIH, especially T lymphocyte-mediated inflammation and cytokine storm-associated liver destruction. Our data in this study show that ORI provides a prominent hepatoprotective effect against Con-A-induced autoimmune hepatitis, as indicated by decrease of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) activity to normal levels, elevation of superoxide dismutase (SOD) level and suppression of IL-6

The peak level of ALT activity after Con-A treatment indicates a large amount of damage to hepatocytes by T cell-mediated cytotoxicity and inflammatory response. ORI greatly decreased ALT levels, indicating the stability of liver cell membranes and reduction of immuno-mediation injury. Such event represents a typical sign for autoimmune hepatitis.^[15] ALT is also a sensitive diagnostic marker of the hepatocyte membrane integrity, and elevated serum levels usually results from leakage caused by insult of inflammation or toxic substances.^[3] Consistent with other reports, Con-A treatment in the current model led to a significant elevation in serum ALT levels, reflecting extensive hepatocellular necrotic liver injury caused by activated CD4⁺ T cells and inflammatory factors. Moreover, ALT activity was markedly decreased in the ORI-treated group, indicating protection of hepatocyte membrane integrity and suppression of immune-related cytotoxicity. This may be due to the preventive effects of ORI on immune cell infiltration and inflammatory signaling pathways that otherwise favor hepatocyte damage.^[16] The hepatoprotective effects were found in bioactive compounds that inhibit T cell activation and reduce the secretion of inflammatory cytokines in Con-A-induced hepatitis models.^[12]

Oxidative stress is in the center of the pathogenic processes of AIH, in its role as a trigger or aggravating factor for immune-mediated liver damage. Overproduction of basal ROS during Con-A-induced immune stimulation results in an overload of endogenous antioxidant systems, which results in lipid peroxidation, mitochondrial dysfunction and hepatocyte apoptosis.^[2] The reduced activity of SOD after Con-A challenge reported in this study is corroborative of the role that ROS play in the development and progression of disease, and is

consistent with previous studies reporting decreased antioxidants defense systems during experimental or clinical AIH.^[5]

Administration of ORI efficiently recovered SOD activity, suggesting also that the endogenous antioxidant capacity and redox homeostasis were ameliorated.^[3] It is suggested that by scavenging superoxide radicals and decreasing the accumulation of ROS, ORI may protect cellular macromolecules from oxidative damage, maintaining the structure and function of hepatocytes. This antioxidant effect may also mediate an indirect reduction in inflammatory signaling, given that oxidative stress can activate redox-sensitive transcriptional factors like NF- κ B and thereby lead to inducible pro-inflammatory cytokine expression. Therefore, fortification of antioxidant measures is a major mechanism involved in the hepatoprotective actions of ORI.

IL-6 is a multifunctional cytokine which is involved in the pathogenesis of AIH through T-cell activation, proliferation of Th17 cells, and induction of inflammatory cascades.^[9] High levels of IL-6 highly correlate with the severity of disease, cytokine storm and liver necrosis in Con-A-mediated hepatitis. In the current study, treatment with Con-A led to a substantial elevation in the IL-6 levels, supporting its pivotal role in immune-mediated liver injury.

Of interest, ORI treatment significantly inhibited IL-6 expression, which indicates its powerful anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory effects. Decreases in IL-6 may reduce downstream activation of STAT3 signaling and lower the recruitment and activation of inflammatory immune cells in the liver.^[17] Such modulation of cytokine networks is crucial to dampen uncontrolled immune responses and abrogating the subsequent development of fulminant hepatitis. ORI's potential in inhibiting IL-6 is also consistent with studies reported that IL-6 targeting agents can reduce immune-mediated liver injury and hepatic complications.^[18]

Collectively, the results of this study indicate that ORI is able to protect against Con-A-induced autoimmune liver injury by a complex mechanism, including membrane stabilization in hepatocytes, potentiation of antioxidant defenses and inhibition of proinflammatory cytokine signaling. The concomitant control of ALT, SOD and IL-6 highlights the interrelation between oxidative stress and immune-induced inflammation during AIH development. Concomitant suppression of these associated pathways, ORI may serve as an effective candidate for treating autoimmune and inflammatory liver diseases.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The data of the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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